

ISic1577

I.Sicily inscription 1577

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

(?)

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Selinus

Place of origin (modern)

Selinunte

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]παρευς

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284905

EDR 112488

EDCS 41300087

PHI 175701

Bibliography

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1973. Iscrizioni greche lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelika* 6. Palermo. At 103

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 343 no.3
Manni Piraino, M.T. 1963. Iscrizioni inedite e revisioni selinuntine. *Kokalos*. 9:
137-156. At 152 n.33
Garbini, G 1964-1965. intervento. *Kokalos*. 10-11: 484-485.
Guarducci, M. 1964-1965. Gli alfabeti della Sicilia arcaica. *Kokalos*. 10-11:
465-488. At 487-488

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1577. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4354532>